

Laparoscopic ventral Hernia Repair under Spinal Anaesthesia: A Feasibility Study

Baidyanath Rajak¹, Jitendra Kumar²

¹Senior Resident, Department of General Surgery, Government Medical College & Hospital, Purnea, Bihar, India

²MD, Department of Anaesthesia, Aashirwad Nursing Home, Purnia, Bihar, India

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Baidyanath Rajak

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Abstract:

This pilot study examined the practicality and effectiveness of spinal anaesthesia in 60 patients who were having laparoscopic transabdominal preperitoneal (TAPP) repair of inguinal hernias at the Government Medical College and Hospital in Purnia, Bihar. The study showed that spinal anaesthesia was successful in managing postoperative pain, as indicated by the low scores on the Visual Analogue Scale. It also helped patients to start moving early and have shorter hospital stays, typically lasting just over 1 day. There were few complications, with only a temporary issue of urinary retention seen in a small number of patients. In general, the majority of patients expressed a high level of satisfaction, with an overwhelming 98% of participants stating their preference for spinal anaesthesia in any future similar procedures. Based on the results, it appears that using spinal anaesthesia instead of general anaesthesia for laparoscopic hernia repairs has proven to be a reliable option. This approach provides advantages in terms of safety, efficiency, and patient contentment.

Keywords: Spinal Anesthesia, Laparoscopic Hernia Repair, Postoperative Pain, Patient Satisfaction.

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Introduction

One of the most frequently conducted surgical procedures globally is the repair of inguinal hernias. Surgeons have developed different surgical approaches to enhance patient outcomes and reduce complications [1]. Out of all the available techniques, the laparoscopic transabdominal preperitoneal (TAPP) method has gained popularity for its advantages such as decreased postoperative pain, quicker recovery, and lower chances of recurrence when compared to the conventional open surgery [2]. Usually conducted while the patient is under general anaesthesia, there is potential to reap additional advantages by considering alternative anaesthesia methods such as spinal anaesthesia. These benefits may include shorter hospital stays and decreased systemic effects [3,4]. Spinal anaesthesia has shown to be effective in various abdominal surgeries and could be a viable choice for laparoscopic hernia repairs [5]. It offers the advantage of decreased cardiopulmonary complications, which is particularly beneficial for patients who are at a higher risk or have significant comorbidities. Furthermore, the use of spinal anaesthesia has the potential to speed up postoperative recovery by avoiding the respiratory depressant effects of general anaesthesia. Research has shown that this can result in better patient throughput and increased satisfaction [6,7].

This pilot study seeks to assess the practicality, safety, and effectiveness of utilising spinal anaesthesia in the laparoscopic transabdominal preperitoneal repair of inguinal hernias. This study aims to gather preliminary data that could potentially lead to larger, more conclusive trials by examining clinical outcomes such as pain control, recovery times, and overall patient satisfaction. Through this investigation, we aim to expand the range of anaesthesia options for laparoscopic hernia repair. We strive to customise anaesthesia techniques to meet the specific needs of each patient, ultimately enhancing the overall surgical experience.

Methodology

Study Design: This pilot study employs a prospective, observational design to assess the efficacy and safety of spinal anaesthesia in patients undergoing laparoscopic transabdominal preperitoneal (TAPP) repair of inguinal hernias.

Study Setting: The study will be conducted at the Government Medical College and Hospital in Purnia, Bihar, over 12 months.

Participants: The trial will include 60 laparoscopically-eligible inguinal hernia patients. Patients 18 to 65 years old, ASA physical status I-

III, and informed consent are eligible. Patients with contraindications to spinal anaesthesia (coagulopathy, puncture site infection, severe spinal deformities), persistent pain, long-term opioid usage, or refusal to participate are excluded.

Anesthesia Procedure

A qualified anaesthesiologist will provide spinal anaesthesia to eligible individuals. Standard monitoring includes electrocardiography, non-invasive blood pressure, and pulse oximetry. The patient's height and weight will determine the hyperbaric bupivacaine (0.5%) dose used to block sensation up to the T10 dermatome level.

Surgical Procedure

Expert surgeons will perform all surgeries using TAPP. The normal TAPP method will be followed, including peritoneal flap construction, hernia reduction, and mesh coverage of the myopectineal orifice without tension.

Data Collection

Preoperative, intraoperative, and postoperative data will be obtained. Demographics, medical history, and baseline health will be collected preoperatively. Intraoperative data includes surgery duration, anaesthetic use, and complications. Visual Analogue Scale (VAS) pain scores at 1, 6, 12, and 24 hours post-surgery, time to first mobilisation, hospital stay, and complications will be recorded.

Outcome Measures

The primary outcome measures will be the feasibility of performing TAPP under spinal anaesthesia, pain control as evidenced by VAS scores, and safety profile characterized by the incidence of complications. Secondary outcomes will include patient satisfaction, recovery times, and hospital discharge readiness.

Statistical Analysis

Descriptive statistics will summarise data. Continuous variables will be shown as means and standard deviations, while categorical variables as frequencies and percentages. The distribution of variables and hypotheses will determine the statistical tests performed to analyse the data.

Results

60 patients undergoing laparoscopic transabdominal preperitoneal repair of inguinal hernias were successfully enrolled in the study.

Most of the participants were male, which is consistent with the higher occurrence of inguinal hernias in men. The participants' ages varied from 18 to 65 years, with an average age of 45 years. The patients were categorised into ASA physical status I-III, with the majority (70%) falling into ASA I. All 60 cases underwent successful administration of spinal anaesthesia, without any requirement to switch to general anaesthesia. The surgery lasted for an average of 75 minutes. A dose of 12.5 mg of hyperbaric bupivacaine was typically administered. There were no complications during the surgery involving spinal anaesthesia, and all planned surgical procedures were successfully carried out without any notable problems.

Postoperative Pain Control

Pain scores measured using the Visual Analog Scale (VAS) showed effective pain control. The average pain scores were as follows:

- 1-hour post-operation: VAS 2
- 6 hours post-operation: VAS 3
- 12 hours post-operation: VAS 2
- 24 hours post-operation: VAS 1

These scores indicate that spinal anaesthesia provided adequate pain management in the immediate postoperative period.

Recovery and Hospital Stay

The time to first mobilization averaged 4 hours post-surgery, with patients being able to walk with minimal assistance. The average length of hospital stay was 1.2 days, with 95% of patients being discharged within 24 hours post-surgery.

Complications and Safety

Postoperative complications were minimal and included transient urinary retention in 5 patients (8.3%), which resolved with conservative management. There were no serious complications such as deep vein thrombosis, pulmonary complications, or anaesthesia-related morbidity.

Patient Satisfaction

Patient satisfaction was assessed via a standardized questionnaire before discharge, revealing high satisfaction levels with the anaesthesia technique and overall surgical experience. Approximately 98% of patients reported they would choose spinal anaesthesia again for similar surgical procedures.

Table 1: This table provides a structured overview of the study outcomes, which can be useful for presentations, discussions, or further analysis.

Category	Details
Number of Patients	60
Gender Distribution	90% male, 10% female
Average Age	45 years (Range: 18-65 years)
ASA Physical Status	70% ASA I, 25% ASA II, 5% ASA III
Average Surgery Duration	75 minutes
Anesthesia Type	Spinal
Average Dose of Bupivacaine	12.5 mg
Intraoperative Complications	None
Average VAS Pain Scores	1 hr: 2, 6 hrs: 3, 12 hrs: 2, 24 hrs: 1
Time to First Mobilization	4 hours
Average Hospital Stay	1.2 days
Postoperative Complications	8.3% (5 patients with transient urinary retention)
Patient Satisfaction	98% would choose spinal anesthesia again

Discussion

The results of this pilot study indicate that spinal anaesthesia is a very successful approach for pain management during and after laparoscopic transabdominal preperitoneal (TAPP) repair of inguinal hernias [8,9]. The reported pain scores at different postoperative intervals (VAS scores of 2, 3, 2, and 1 at 1, 6, 12, and 24 hours, respectively) highlight the effectiveness of this treatment in managing postoperative discomfort [10]. The findings of this study support previous research indicating that spinal anaesthesia may offer better pain relief in the immediate aftermath of surgery compared to general anaesthesia. This is likely because the analgesic effect is focused and concentrated in a specific area. This study highlights a notable benefit of utilising spinal anaesthesia: faster postoperative recovery times. After surgery, patients were able to start moving around within an average of 4 hours. Their hospital stay typically lasted just over 1 day, according to studies [13,14]. These results have proven to be highly advantageous in alleviating overcrowding in hospitals and lowering healthcare expenses. They provide a practical solution in environments where quick patient turnover is crucial. In addition, it is of utmost importance to prevent respiratory complications related to general anaesthesia in patients who are older or have pre-existing respiratory problems [15,16].

The study found a low complication rate, with only 8.3% of participants experiencing transient urinary retention. This side effect, which is known and can be managed, is associated with spinal anaesthesia. The low rate of complications indicates that spinal anaesthesia is both effective and safe for patients who are undergoing laparoscopic hernia repairs [17]. Nevertheless, it is crucial to take into account

that the study's sample size and single-center design might restrict the applicability of the results. It would be advantageous to conduct larger, multicenter trials to validate these findings and potentially establish spinal anaesthesia as a standard practice for similar procedures [18]. Ensuring patient satisfaction is a crucial factor when evaluating the viability of new medical practices. The study reveals a remarkable satisfaction rate of 98% among patients, emphasising the significant advantages of spinal anaesthesia in terms of patient-centered care. Many participants expressed a preference for spinal anaesthesia for future similar procedures, suggesting that it is well-accepted and potentially preferred over general anaesthesia.

This pilot study lays the foundation for future research [19]. Future research should strive to incorporate a broader range of patients and consider utilising a randomised controlled trial format to directly compare with general anaesthesia. Such studies could investigate not only the clinical outcomes but also the economic impacts of utilizing spinal versus general anaesthesia, taking into account both direct and indirect costs [20].

Conclusion

This pilot study suggests that spinal anaesthesia can be a suitable and efficient alternative to general anaesthesia for laparoscopic transabdominal preperitoneal repair of inguinal hernias. It provides notable advantages in terms of pain management, recovery times, and patient satisfaction. Spinal anaesthesia has proven to be highly effective, with minimal complications and excellent patient satisfaction. It enables patients to regain mobility faster and spend less time in the hospital,

suggesting its potential for wider use in similar surgeries. The results of this study are encouraging and highlight the importance of conducting additional research. It is recommended to carry out larger, multicenter randomised trials to validate these findings and explore the potential benefits of using spinal anaesthesia in laparoscopic surgeries.

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